

REPRESENTATION OF DEICTIC SIGNS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK POLITICAL TEXTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14575424>

Abstract. *In this research work, the use of deictic signs in English and Uzbek political texts, their semantic and pragmatic signs and communicative functions are analyzed. Deixis is seen as one of the main tools in enhancing the meaning of political texts and establishing a useful dialogue with the audience. In this article, the use of person, space, and time deixis in Uzbek and English political texts is studied by comparing them with each other. At the same time, the place of these tools in the linguistic and sociolinguistic context is analyzed. According to the results of scientific research, cultural and contextual factors influencing the specific use of deixis in each language have been identified. This research contributes to a deeper study of political texts from the point of view of linguistics.*

Keywords: *political texts, English and Uzbek languages, deictic signs, modern linguistics, content, communicative process, effective, semantic features, grammatical, theoretically, practical point, cultural context, historical.*

Introduction. The topic of this research work is one of the current directions of modern linguistics and occupies a special place in the semantic and pragmatic analysis of political texts. Today, in the process of globalization, which is rapidly developing, the need for deep understanding of the content of political texts in different languages, their correct translation and effective communicative use is increasing. In particular, linguistic tools such as deictic signs play an important role in understanding the contextual content of a political text and its correct interpretation. Let's focus on the essence of the topic here for a better understanding of the topic.

Deixis is a branch of linguistics that studies language tools that show the relationship between subject, object and reality during the communicative process. The use of deictic signs is based on the grammatical and semantic features of each language in its own way. There are differences in the expression of deixis in English and Uzbek, which can cause difficulties in understanding and translating political texts. For this reason, the study of this topic is important not only theoretically, but also from a practical point of view.

Literature analysis. The conducted research includes the study of deictic signs in English and Uzbek languages. J. Levinson's theory of deixis is widely used in English linguistics, and according to him, deixis is emphasized as a universal feature of language. [1] Levinson's research discusses the importance of deixis in political discourse. In Uzbek linguistics, deixis was studied in different contexts in the researches of A. Nurmonov and S. Madrakhimov. They further shed light on the national peculiarities of deixis in Uzbek political texts. [2], [3]

In the analyzed literature, mutual compatibility and differences in the use of deictic tools are also highlighted. Although the use of personal deixis in English and Uzbek political speeches is similar, some differences can be seen in the use of space and time deixis. In English speech, spatial deixis are used to express the global scale, while in Uzbek speech, they have a more local character. In the deixis of time, on the contrary, universal terms are used more often in English speeches, while in Uzbek speeches, the historical and cultural context is of great importance.

Based on the opinions of scientists who have conducted research in this direction, a space is a place where the speaker or author and interlocutor or reader occupy a place in the process of communication, and where the activity is performed or happened. Most scholars say that here, there, over there are recognized as means of deixis of space in English, and in Uzbek - bu yerda, shu yerda, u yerda, u yoqda, o'sha yerda. [4]

Methodology. As a result of scientific research in the field of linguistics, significant progress is being made in the field of pragmalinguistics. In particular, in the process of studying the types of deixis, research is being conducted in such directions as discourse deixis, social deixis, and emotional deixis. Among the types of deixis, personal deixis is one of the most common forms and is located in the central part of the deixis field. In speech communication, personal deixis is formed depending on the place of the participants. The first person indicates the speaker and serves as a linguistic device to refer to oneself, the second person represents the listener or addressee, and the third person refers to a person who is not directly involved in the communication.

This system is expressed mainly through pronouns and is differentiated based on categories such as person, number and gender. However, a plural pronoun does not always correspond directly to a singular form. For example, the pronoun "we" does not always refer to a plurality of speakers, and the correct understanding of its meaning depends on the context. For example, the listener of the English sentence "We translate all these texts ourselves" has two possible realizations: he can add himself to the group or not. Therefore, the exclusive (speaker and others, not the addressee) and inclusive (including both the speaker and the addressee) forms of the pronoun "we" are distinguished. In some languages, these differences are clearly expressed grammatically. For example, the speech of the President of the USA D. Trump can be a bright example in this regard.

When analyzing the means of expressing personal deixis, it should not be forgotten that third-person pronouns should be considered as a separate group in the language system. Research shows that the pronouns of this group are significantly different from other personal pronouns with their semantic and communicative features. The first and second person pronouns, i.e. "I" and "you", are direct participants in communication and represent "communicative persons", while the third person pronouns are not directly related to such communication. They usually represent "non-communicative individuals". Another type of deixis is spatial deixis, which refers to a place or location. In Uzbek linguistics, this type is studied as a deix of space. Showing the location of the participants in the process of communication constitutes the content of the deixis of the space. Perception of reality and its linguistic expression require two main thinking processes: first, description of reality and then placing it in a certain space.

Deictic devices representing locativeness are used to determine whether persons and objects are located near or far from the place of speech communication. Such a description can be made not only in relation to the speaker's position, but also to the addressee's position. Also, the direction in which the movement occurs can affect the use of deictic tools. According to the scholars who have conducted research on deixis, spatial deixis performs the tasks of pointing, showing or reminding the place occupied by the speaker or writer and the interlocutor or reader, as well as the place where the action is performed. Many scientists recognize such combinations as here, there, over there in English, and in Uzbek as means of deixis of space. [5]

Personality deixis is one of the most frequently used deictic markers in political texts. In political speeches in English, personal pronouns such as "we" and "I" serve as the main means of

demonstrating the solidarity of the politician with the audience. For example, in the speeches of US President Barack Obama, the pronoun “we” is often used to create an image that unites the nation. This tendency is also observed in Uzbek political texts. For example, in the speeches of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the pronoun “we” is widely used, and a feeling of closeness to the people is evoked. With the help of this personal deixis, politicians try to present themselves as part of the people and try to emphasize that they are working for them.

Spatial deixis also feature prominently in political texts. In English, the use of deictic signs such as “here” and “there” makes the content of the text clearer and meaningful. For example, in phrases like “Here, in this great nation...” the pronoun “here” is used to increase national pride. In Uzbek language, expressions such as “bu yerda” and “shu chog’da” perform exactly this task. In Shavkat Mirziyoyev’s speeches, expressions such as “at this important meeting” or “this country” not only enhance the content of the speech, but also evoke a sense of regional closeness in the audience.

Tense deixis is considered one of the main means of defining time in the semantics of political texts and conveying a message to the target audience. In English, deixis such as “now”, “then”, “today” are widely used. For example, the phrase “Now is the time for change” is used to emphasize the urgency of the current situation. In Uzbek language, deixis such as “hozir”, “bugun”, “shu kunlarda” are common. With the help of time deixis in political texts, politicians manage to make their speech dynamic and current.

Discussion and results. A better understanding can also be gained through these examples. For example, the sentence of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “We are building a new Uzbekistan” shows that deixis in Uzbek political texts are aimed at expressing the national spirit. In English, Obama’s phrase “Yes, we can” was seen as a force that united the people. More precisely, the study of deictic signs in English and Uzbek political texts has an important feature for linguistics and cultural communication. The analysis of these texts sheds light on how politicians use language to achieve their goals and shows how deixis are unique to each language and culture.

According to the results of the conducted scientific research, the function of deictic symbols in political texts is to directly strengthen the connection between the participants of the dialogue, to emphasize the relevance of the events, and to clarify the content of the dialogue. We can see that the deixis of person, space and time are used a lot in English and Uzbek political texts. Although these deixis are used interdependently, there are differences in their usage according to linguistic and cultural traditions. Deixis and their use in political texts focus on social context and audience. Political discourse in English is often aimed at a global audience, and deixis is used to emphasize commonality. In Uzbek language, deixis based on national values and historical traditions strengthen the sincerity of the text and the national characteristics of communication.

These studies indicate that deixis is important in the effective delivery of political discourse in both languages. However, the usefulness of these tools depends on how well they are adapted to the meaning and context. For example, in political texts in English, temporal-spatial deixis like here and now are used to reveal broader global issues. In Uzbek speeches, such deixis emphasize national issues and historical events. According to the results, the use of deixis in political texts shows not only the linguistic aspect, but also the sociolinguistic and pragmatic aspects of communication. This makes the content of political speech more effective and closer to the audience.

Conclusion. Deictic signs and their use in English and Uzbek political texts show that deictic signs are pragmatically, sociolinguistically, and communicatively important. And these tools, in addition to increasing the effectiveness of political speech, play a large and important role in creating communication between speech participants and conveying the meaning of communication more clearly. Deixis is used in political speeches not only as a language tool, but also as a political strategy. Deixis strengthen the spiritual and emotional connection between the participants of the dialogue and serve to effectively deliver the political message.

In the near future, a more in-depth study of the specific use of deixis in different cultures and languages will contribute to enriching their linguistic and pragmatic possibilities. Also, preserving the meaning and function of deixis during the translation of political texts requires special attention. The results of this research reveal new aspects of linguistic analysis of political texts and create a basis for more effective use of communication strategies.

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